

Status of job satisfaction and workplace conditions of faculty teachers of Rajasthan University, Jaipur

Priya Shukla¹, Dr. Gurudatt Kakkar², Shalabh Shukla³, K Rathna⁴, AC Tripathi⁵

^{1,2}Department of Commerce and Management, Career Point University, Kota Rajasthan, India

³ Department of Agriculture Science, Career Point University, Kota, Rajasthan, India

⁴ Department of Finance, Himalayan University, Itanagar, Arunachal Pradesh, India

⁵ Chief Executive Officer, Sanjeevani Foundation for Health Education and Environment Research Action, New Delhi, India

Abstract

Teachers are an important part in building the nation and budding citizens of the nation. Job satisfaction is an important concept that is not only related to an individual but it is relevant for the society's well-being. Job satisfaction among teachers is one factor that will ensure class performance and productivity of schools. Job satisfaction is the combination of emotional and psychological experience at any work. Job Satisfaction is the relationship between what everyone expects in accordance to what everyone achieves. A faculty in an Institute plays an important part in developing the knowledge and skills of youth. This study aims at investigating the job satisfaction among faculty teachers and their work place condition in Rajasthan. The site surveyed, data was collected and six variable parameters explained the nature of the management, participation and freedom in decision making, discharges of routine work, Inter-personal relationship, parental care and parent support and student's attitude and involvement. There were respondent's opinion towards the nature of the management and there are five positive statements raised by the researcher. Workplace conditions, professional development and infrastructure significantly create overall job satisfaction of the teaching faculty. Strategic attention need to be given specifically for the compensation dimension which is closely associated with overall job satisfaction.

Keywords: job satisfaction, workplace condition, faculty teachers

1. Introduction

There are three principle levels of qualifications within the degree structure of Indian higher education system; the bachelor/undergraduate level, master's/post-graduate level and doctoral/pre-doctoral level; also included are diploma courses at undergraduate and post graduate level. Management institutes are a part of higher education system, determine the career paths of the youth and in turn the future of the country. Students, parents, teachers, staff and society in general are the stakeholders of these institutes. Faculty members, the core eighty percent human resource of any management institute, have the potential and power to transform the future generation of our country.

Role of faculty teachers in the society and in the education can change, but the importance of their position remains same. To attract and retain the quality faculty teacher is a great challenge with the educational institutions. In education, the essential quality of the teacher is to have a positive approach. Every teacher must have the potential and clear intention to discharge their duty with utmost devotion to derive satisfaction from their work.

Faculty job satisfaction levels seem to have direct bearing on the institutional as well as the student development and an understanding of job satisfaction, retention and employee turnover aspects of the faculties would help policy makers understand a very important organ of the society, responsible for future of the nation and generation.

Job satisfaction is the combination of emotional and psychological experience at any work. Job Satisfaction is the direct relationship between what everyone expects in

accordance to what everyone achieves. Any work cannot be effectively done without satisfaction.

Most of the higher educational institutes throughout the country are suffering from acute shortage of faculty, not to mention good faculty members. To face faculty crisis, educational institutes opt for ad hoc, part time or visiting faculties who teach only for a few couple of hours. These faculties are least committed towards the institute; as they work in multiple places to make a living. They are thus frustrated and not motivated.

Job satisfaction is the state of feelings towards the job undertaken by an employee either positively or negatively. Job satisfaction is a pleasurable emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job ^[1]. It is an affective reaction to one's job ^[2]. It is also called an attitude towards one's job ^[3].

Teachers are important in building the nation and budding citizens of the nation. So, job satisfaction is an important concept that is not only related to an individual but it is relevant for the society's well-being. Job satisfaction is one factor that will ensure class performance and productivity of schools. The teachers would get interested to teach their students effectively when they are satisfied with their jobs ^[4]. Like India, other countries in the world are trying to improve their quality of education, so that it meets the demand of globalization.

Alagbari (2003) who found out that the satisfying factors were salary, achievement, relationships with teachers, compatibility between qualifications, experience and work, social status and job security ^[5]. Teachers would perform to

maximum capacity, only if they are satisfied with their jobs. The job satisfaction is an important phenomenon in every sector especially in the teaching profession. The present paper aims to study the status of job satisfaction towards work place condition of faculty teachers in Rajasthan.

2. Methodology

Site selected for the study was self-financing Arts and Science Colleges affiliated to Rajasthan University, Jaipur.

Research Design

The research is descriptive in nature and includes surveys, fact-findings, and inquiries from different groups. In order to retain objectivity every attempt was made to take an unbiased sample. The study is a combination of both exploratory and descriptive one in nature. A well-structured questionnaire was prepared for considering workplace

conditions and calculating the level of job satisfaction among the teaching faculty of self-financing Arts and Science Colleges, affiliated to Rajasthan University, Jaipur.

3. Result and Discussion

The site was surveyed and the information collected on different parameters of the job satisfaction of the teaching faculty towards the workplace conditions. It was observed that there are six variable in parameter that explains the nature of the management, participation and freedom in decision making, discharges of routine work, Inter-personal relationship, parental care and parent support and students attitude and involvement.

The table 1 describes the respondent’s opinion towards the nature of the management. There are five positive statements raised by the researcher.

Table 1: Satisfactory level of the respondents towards nature of the management

S. No.	Nature of the Management	SA	A	NAND	DA	SD
1	The management is supportive and encouraging	117 (29.25)	79 (19.75)	81 (20.25)	34 (8.5)	89 (22.25)
2	The administrators clearly define the college policy	46 (11.5)	86 (21.5)	65 (16.25)	94 (23.5)	109 (27.25)
3	Access to management is good and easy	36 (9)	67 (16.75)	139 (34.75)	45 (11.25)	113 (28.25)
4	The style of the management is good	43 (10.75)	43 (10.75)	117 (29.25)	118 (29.5)	79 (19.75)
5	There is a good treatment	36 (9)	67 (16.75)	139 (34.75)	49 (12.25)	109 (27.25)

Source: Primary Data

SA- Strongly agree; A- Agree; NAND – Neither agree nor disagree; DA – Disagree; SD – Strongly Disagree

The following are the responses of the respondents

i. Nature of the Management

a. The Management is supportive and encouraging: Out of the total respondents, 29.25% of the respondent’s strongly agreed that the management is supportive and encouraging the teaching faculty. Another 19.75% of the respondents agreed with the statement. The highest 49% of the respondent’s agreed with the statement. It is very much clear that the management is supportive and encouraging academic endeavours.

b. The administrators clearly define the college policies: Among the total respondent’s, 27.25% of the respondent’s strongly disagree, followed by 23.5 % of the respondents who disagree that the administrators clearly define the college policies. Only 11.5% of the respondents strongly agree with the statement.

c. Access to the management is good and easy: The highest percentages of the respondents 34.25% neither agree nor disagree and the second highest percentage 28.25% strongly disagree and another 11.25% disagree that the access to the management was good and easy. Only 9% of the respondents strongly agree with the statement. Therefore, it is understood that the present management is not so flexible and easily accessible to the staff members.

d. The style of the management is good: The highest percentage of the respondents (29.5%) disagree, followed by 19.75 % who strongly disagree that the style of the management is good. Only 10.75 % of the respondents strongly agree and agree respectively with an equally high percentage 29.25%.

e. There is a good treatment: Out of the total, 27.25% of the respondents strongly disagree and 12.25% of the

respondents disagree that there is a good treatment from the management of the self-Financing Arts and Science colleges.

ii. Satisfactory level of the respondents towards the nature of the management

a. Management supportive and encouraging:

The highest (29.25%) percentage of the respondents strongly agrees that the management is supportive and encouraging.

b. Management/Administrator clearly defines the college policy: 27.25 % of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement that the administrator clearly defines its policy and only 11.5 % strongly agree with the statement.

c. Access to management is good and easy: 28.25% of the respondents strongly disagree and 11.25% of the respondents disagree that access to the management is easy and good.

d. The style of the management is good: 29.5% of the respondents disagree that style of the management is good and is making it interesting to fulfil the academic venture.

e. There is a good treatment: 27.25% of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement that there is a good treatment from the management. 44.25% of the respondents have given fourth rank to the workplace conditions. The lowest (4.25%) percentage of the respondents has given first rank.

4. Conclusion

Job satisfaction is the fulfilment of one’s expectation from job. It is a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job experience. But the

expectation of people may not be homogeneous. It may differ from person to person, place to place, job to job, context to context, and organization to organization. So, job satisfaction cannot be generalized. From the academic perspective, Workplace conditions, compensation, infrastructure and professional development affect the job satisfaction of the teaching faculty.

5. Reference

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